

Effect of Organizational Intelligence Educational Intervention on the Job and Organizational Variables in Sports Managers

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Abstract

The present study aimed to investigate the effect of organizational intelligence educational intervention on sports managers' job and organizational variables. The research method was quasi-experimental with a pre-test, post-test design and the follow-up with a control group. The present study population included all managers and deputies of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Administration at Al-Mustansiriya University selected using the convenience sampling of 20 individuals which were then randomly assigned into two groups - experimental (10 participants) and control (10 participants). The organizational intelligence training was conducted for the managers of the experimental group (in 8 sessions). The data collection tools included the 20-item Job Satisfaction Questionnaire by Martin J. Gannon (2010), 10-item Job Attachment Questionnaire by Kanungo (1982), 36-item Job Adjustment Questionnaire by De Lauf Quest (1984), 13-item Hill Citizenship Organizational Behavior Questionnaire by Hill (2002), 24-item Strategic Thinking Questionnaire (Jane Lidka, 2008), Lawson's (2003) 24-item Knowledge Management Questionnaire, as well as the Riggs and Knight (1994) 36-item Job Self-Efficacy Questionnaire. Multivariate analysis of variance and repeated measures analysis of variance were conducted. According to the results, there was a significant difference between the mean scores of the three stages of pre-test, post-test and follow-up of job satisfaction, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy. Accordingly, organizational intelligence training had a significant effect on job variables, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy. This effect had significant stability on these variables after three months.

Introduction

Like other organizations, sports organizations need to strengthen their employees' organizational intelligence to succeed and gain a competitive edge. Psychologists have used the structure of intelligence to describe the overall ability of the individual. In addition, experts in management and organization in recent years have used the structure of organizational intelligence in describing organizations. In organizations, intelligence is considered a general ability or talent that affects individual and organizational identity and causes individual, group and organizational effectiveness and efficiency. In the 1980s, Gardner proposed several independent and separate intelligence units for individual intelligence under the heading of individual multiple intelligences. By developing the theory, he provided the ground for more attention to different dimensions of intelligence. Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences is still evolving as a dynamic theory (Armstrong, 2019).

In the framework of organizational theories, the intelligence structure has been used to describe organizations' overall ability. Organizational intelligence was first introduced at the Paris Conference by Taki Heiko, Bill, and Matsuda of Isa Hara University in Japan. In this view, organizational intelligence is a general ability discussed under the heading of organizational knowledge and knowledge management. Therefore, organizations include many intelligence components, but not all members and components of intelligence in an organization are concentrated.

According to Albrecht (2010), organizational intelligence is the organization's talent and capacity in achieving organizational goals. Ashnaka (2012) believes that organizational intelligence constitutes an understanding of the organization as a learning system. Chen (2019) considers organizational intelligence as effective decision making. In general, the above definitions show that organizational intelligence is a kind of organizational ability that helps achieve organizational goals and leads to better job adaptation by increasing professional and organizational knowledge.

Pergerin and Vasilak (2007) in their study of sports organizations reported that some features in sports centers could be an obstacle to the development of organizational intelligence. In addition, there are managerial factors and human resources in such centers that provide the possibility of increasing organizational intelligence which, in turn, can enhance individual, organizational variables.

Experts such as McGill Cressitt et al. (2004) after years of study at the University of London and the International Center for Improvement (ISEIC) inspired by Gardner's theory and new organizational perspectives, especially Peter Singh's learning organization theory and organizational intelligence theories in service, industrial, governmental and commercial organizations have adapted the theory of multiple organizational intelligence for training. In doing so, they have been able to bring beneficial results in increasing positive organizational variables (quoted in Robbins, 1397). In this line, the present study is an effort to improve the variables of job satisfaction, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, knowledge management, and strategic thinking by teaching organizational intelligence in the sports organization.

Fletcher (2019) believes that job satisfaction is an act of co-ordination between the needs and professional values of the individual and the work-enhancing system, satisfaction with the progress and stability of the job, which is based on the homogeneity of personality and organization. Kanungo's job attachment(1982) considers job attachment as a description of a person's current job and a function of the extent to which his/her job can meet his current needs (Carmelie, 2016). According to these definitions, job satisfaction and attachment can be aligned. Job adaptation could also be added. Laf Quist and Davis (1991) noted that job adjustment involves adapting one's personality to work-related environmental factors. Therefore, job adjustment is a combination of psychological and non-psychological factors that provide a sense of job satisfaction. Job adjustment can enhance organizational citizenship behavior. Organizational citizen behavior comprises several voluntary honors that employees do to help colleagues; this type of behavior is not part of the duties and responsibilities assigned to the individual (Becker, 2019).

Each variable's presence increases its efficiency and effectiveness, thus helping the organization achieves its real goals. The presence of such variables, along with knowledge management, could lead to improved organizational performance because it injects new knowledge into the organization. Knowledge management is seen as an integrated management plan focusing on strategic goals, moving around business processes and using information technology (Noor, 2016). Knowledge management is related to discovering and promoting an organization's knowledge assets with a vision that advances its goals. The managed knowledge includes explicit and implicit knowledge (mental knowledge of individuals) (Davenport and Prosak, 2016). The variable that is in line with knowledge management is strategic thinking. Strategic thinking is a tool for introducing concepts and approaches. In fact, one who takes the time to reinforce strategic thinking reinforces a way of thinking. The output of thought is not very tangible. Strategic thinking enables managers to understand what factors effectively achieve the desired goals and which ones are not effective and why and how effective factors create value for the customer (Swayan et al., 2019).

The Ministry of Sports is the principal custodian of the country's sports in Iraq, and its performance affects all aspects of socio-cultural and family life. The optimal performance of this ministry seems to be a prerequisite to have a healthy and developed society. On the contrary, its poor performance would lead to many social and cultural dysfunctions. The diversity of sports, cultures, tastes and sports facilities has complicated the Ministry of Sports and Youth's duties. Due to the interaction of various variables, management work in such a ministry is also complex and needs multiple intelligences. Undoubtedly, the Ministry of Sports and Youth must be equipped with high organizational intelligence to achieve its organizational goals. To the best of the researchers' knowledge, in Iraq, no research on organizational intelligence training in sports organizations has been conducted so far; therefore, the present study could be considered the first in its type.

Given the issues raised, the question now arises concerns whether organizational intelligence training can affect the variables of job satisfaction, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy of sports managers. Accordingly, the present study examines the possible effects of organizational intelligence skills training intervention on sports managers' job and organizational variables in Iraq.

Methodology

The research method was quasi-experimental with the pre-test, post-test and follow-up with a control group. The statistical population comprised all principals and deputies of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Administration of Al-Mustansiriya University in 2020. First, 20 participants were selected by available sampling from among the principals and deputies of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sports Department of Al-Mustansiriya University, who had the required criteria to be included in the study. They were, then, randomly divided into two experimental (10 participants) and control groups (10 participants). Then, the organizational intelligence training was presented to the experimental group in 8 sessions of 90 minutes while no intervention was conducted for the control group. At the end of the training sessions, the two groups were re-evaluated through research questionnaires (post-test) and then three months later by a follow-up phase.

In this study, seven measurement instruments were used. The first tool was the 20-item Job Satisfaction Questionnaire by Martin J. Gannon (2010). This questionnaire has five components: job satisfaction, supervisor satisfaction, colleague satisfaction, promotion satisfaction, and salary satisfaction. A higher score indicates more job satisfaction in the individual. Martin J. Gannon (2010) reported concurrent validity with the Smith Questionnaire (1995) 0.50 and the reliability of the questionnaire 0.89. Also, in the present study, a coefficient of 0.81 was obtained.

The second tool was the 10-item Job Attachment Questionnaire by Kanungo(1982). Kanungo (1982) reported concurrent validity coefficient (with Robert Job Interest Questionnaire) and reliability of the questionnaire 0.61 and 0.84, respectively. Moreover, in the present study, a coefficient of 0.84 was obtained.

The third instrument was the 36-item Job Adjustment Questionnaire by De Laugh Quest (1984). The questionnaire had six components: progress value, convenience value, base value, altruistic value, safety value, and autonomy value. De Laugh Quest (1984) reported its convergence validity with Fouckel (1980) compatibility questionnaire 0.63 and the reliability of the questionnaire 0.85. Also, in the present study, a coefficient of 0.88 was obtained.

The fourth instrument was Hill's (2002)13-item Questionnaire on Organizational Citizenship Behavior. The questionnaire had three components: supportive behaviors, social etiquette and chivalry. Hill (2002) reported its convergence validity with Zack (1993) Organizational Behavior Questionnaire 0.52 and the reliability of the questionnaire 0.89. Furthermore, in the present study, a coefficient of 0.83 was obtained.

The fifth tool was the 24-Question Strategic Thinking Questionnaire by Jane Lidka (2008) which has five components: system vision, intention focus, intelligent opportunism, time thinking, and hypothesis-based thinking. Lidka (2008) reported its convergence validity with Al-Bakhtar (1990) organizational intelligence questionnaire 0.58 and the questionnaire's reliability as 0.86. In the present study, a coefficient of 0.84 was obtained.

The sixth tool was the Lawson's (2003) 24-Question Knowledge Management Questionnaire with six components: knowledge creation, knowledge acquisition, knowledge organization, knowledge storage, knowledge dissemination, and knowledge application. Lawson (2003) reported its convergence validity with the Knowledge-Based Organization Questionnaire (1996) 0.63 and the reliability of the questionnaire 0.90. Also, in the present study, a coefficient of 0.89 was obtained.

The final tool was the 36-item Job Self-efficacy Questionnaire by Riggs and Knight (1994). It has four components: individual self-efficacy beliefs, individual outcome expectations, collective effectiveness beliefs, and collective outcome expectations. Riggs and Knight (1994) reported its convergence validity with the Scherer self-efficacy questionnaire (189) 0.55 and the reliability of the questionnaire 0.82. In the present study, a coefficient of 0.84 was obtained.

The present research educational protocol was designed based on theoretical foundations and research related to organizational intelligence as well as the model adapted from Al-Bakhtar(2003) with the focus on improving sports managers' organizational intelligence skills. It was approved in relation to the seven skills, lesson plan and course titles of each training session by sports management specialists (5 people) and professors in industrial-organizational psychology (2 people). The items in the training protocol included lectures, brochures, group discussions, questions and answers, and training as well as simulation of organizational intelligence skills for all managers in the experimental research group. Topics covered in each session were related to one of the seven skills of organizational intelligence (strategic vision, shared destiny, desire for change, unity and agreement, morale, application of the knowledge and performance pressure) regarding academic sports managers in relation to their students, partner groups as well as the university. The research training protocol was presented separately for each session, including the following cases and topics.

Session 1: Training to recognize and understand organizational goals in different dimensions and levels; training on the application of strategic goals for the organization; training to recognize the importance and acceptance of organizational goals for employees and coordination between goals and employee behavior with strategic goals; teaching strategic management concepts and ways of setting goals for the organization in the strategic dimension as well as evaluating the strategic goals of the organization and the methods of reviewing those goals based on the feedback obtained from the annual evaluations in sports organizations.

Session 2: Teaching the importance of the sense of belonging among employees and the organization on the one hand and the organizational goals on the other hand; teaching the concepts of organizational trust and the importance of promoting it in achieving organizational goals; teaching the importance of mutual understanding between individuals; working groups and the organization and efforts to increase empathy and collaboration of efforts between employees and the organization in organizations with a focus on sports.

Session 3: Teaching the importance of change in the organization and especially in today's changing world; teaching the concepts of change management and its importance in advancing organizational goals; teaching the importance of accepting change in employees and ways to do it; training change management in the organization during organizational crises and crisis management in sports organizations.

Session 4: Teaching the importance of employees having a positive attitude towards the job as well as the work environment in the organization; teaching the factors affecting employees' motivation and job motivation; and teaching how to benefit from and promote employee job motivation in sports organizations and its management correctly and effectively.

Session 5: Teaching the importance of unity among employees in relation to achieving organizational goals; teaching the components of empathy in professional and organizational environments and trying to promote empathy between employees in working groups and in carrying out job projects; teaching the requirements for team activities in the organization for employees and paying attention to setting rules, respecting the rules and paying attention to delegating authority in performing team and organizational activities in order to achieve and promote unity and empathy among employees in sports organizations.

Session 6: Teaching the importance of benefiting and using the organization of up-to-date knowledge in order to achieve organizational goals; teaching the importance of knowledge management and elaborating on its components, as well as how to use it in the organization in relation to employees and working groups, teaching how to achieve the knowledge related to the organization and organizational goals as well as the application of knowledge in the job and organization; teaching the importance and methods of sharing information in the organization and work environment in sports organizations.

Session 7: Teaching the importance of fit between the individual and organizational expectations and explicating methods for establishing a balance between expectations, expectations and job and professional duties of employees with the organization's expectations of employees; teaching the importance of transparency and articulating organizational goals and trying to understand the organization's expectations from employees as well as understanding the needs and expectations of employees from the organization; teaching the importance and how to express organizational goals correctly and understandably to employees in the organization; teaching the importance of feedback on job productivity and also teaching how to provide positive and practical feedback to employees to improve their performance in sports organizations. The analysis of variance with repeated measures was used to analyze the data.

Findings

Research Hypothesis: Organizational intelligence training affects job and organizational variables (job satisfaction, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy) of Iraqi sports managers.

Table 1. Box Test Results Assessing the Variance of Job Satisfaction Scores, Job Attachment, Job Adjustment, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Strategic Thinking, Knowledge Management and Job Self-Efficacy

Variable	F	Degrees of freedom	Box value	Significance
Job satisfaction	2.31	3	7.90	0.07
Job attachment	1.89	3	4.85	0.19
Job compatibility	1.85	3	6.31	0.14
Organizational citizenship behavior	2.13	3	7.24	0.10
Strategic thinking	0.93	3	1.08	0.34
Knowledge management	1.07	3	1.36	0.29
Job self-efficacy	2	3	6.74	0.12

Table 1 shows the Box test results assessing the variance of job satisfaction scores, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self- efficacy. As shown, the observed F for the Box test does not show a significant difference between job satisfaction scores, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy at the 0.05 level and can be used as parametric statistics for inferential data analysis.

Table 2. Results of the Hypothesis of Homogeneity of Regression Slopes

Variable	Mean squares	F	Significance level
Job Satisfaction	2.31	7.90	0.07
Job attachment	1.18	3.87	0.22
Job compatibility	1.02	3.14	0.26
Organizational citizenship behavior	1.55	4.23	0.17
Strategic thinking	2.08	6.25	0.14
Knowledge management	2.24	6.82	0.11
Job self-efficacy	1.29	4.06	0.25

Table 2 displays the results of the hypothesis of homogeneity of regression slopes. As can be observed, since the

F-statistic was not significant, there was no interaction between the pre-test effect (job satisfaction scores, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy) and the independent variable (organizational intelligence training). Therefore, the hypothesis of homogeneity of regression slopes is confirmed.

Table 3. Results of Mauchly'sphericity Test of Sphericity in Repeated Measurements

Variable	Mauchly's test	df	Significance level
Job satisfaction	0.18	2	0.001
Job attachment	0.76	2	0.10
Job compatibility	0.34	2	0.001
Organizational citizenship behavior	0.43	2	0.001
Strategic thinking	0.60	2	0.13
Knowledge management	0.66	2	0.03
Job self-efficacy	0.32	2	0.001

Table 3 shows the results of Mauchly'sphericity test of sphericity in repeated measurements. As indicated, the results show that the Mauchly statistic at the 0.05 level, i.e. the covariances' default uniformity, using the Mauchlytest in some variables, is rejected. However, in some of the variables, it is confirmed. The conservative Greenhouse-Geiser test is used to measure repeated measurement of variance. Table 4 presents the results of multivariate analysis of variance with repeated measures for the effects of intragroup interaction (Wilkes lambda).

Table 4. Results of Multivariate Analysis of Variance with Repeated Measures for the Effects of Intragroup Interaction (Wilkes Lambda)

Test	Factor	Value	F	df error	Significance level	Eta squared
Job satisfaction	Time	0.77	28.07	17	0.001	0.76
	Group and time interaction	0.70	19.57	17	0.001	0.69
Job attachment	Time	0.89	68.31	17	0.001	0.88
	Group and time interaction	0.84	45.35	17	0.001	0.84
Job compatibility	Time	0.84	45.34	17	0.001	0.84
	Group and time interaction	0.77	28.19	17	0.001	0.77
Organizational citizenship behavior	Time	0.73	23.22	17	0.001	0.73
	Group and time interaction	0.62	14.09	17	0.001	0.62
Strategic thinking	Time	0.90	73.55	17	0.001	0.86
	Group and time interaction	0.84	45.73	17	0.001	0.84
Knowledge management	Time	0.93	107.07	17	0.001	0.82
	Group and time interaction	0.88	66.44	17	0.001	0.80
Job self-efficacy	Time	0.71	20.88	17	0.001	0.71
	Group and time interaction	0.59	12.36	17	0.001	0.59

Table 4 and F's results at the level of the relationship between the linear combination of dependent variables (job satisfaction, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy) with the independent variables (organizational intelligence training) are significant. Organizational intelligence training significantly affects at least one of the dependent variables (job satisfaction, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy). Table 5 shows the results of analysis of variance with repeated measures, comparison of pre-test, post-test and follow-up scores of the effect of organizational intelligence training on job satisfaction, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy.

Table 5. Results of Analysis of Variance with Repeated Measures, Comparison of Pre-Test, Post-Test and Follow-Up Scores of the Effect of Organizational Intelligence Training on Job Satisfaction, Job Attachment, Job Adjustment, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Strategic Thinking, Knowledge Management and Job Self-Efficacy

Variable	Sources of change	Total squared	Degree of freedom	Mean squared	F	Significance level	Effect size
Job satisfaction	Time	877.29	2	438.65	48.16	0.001	0.72
	Group and time interaction	578.43	2	239.72	32.25	0.001	0.64
Job attachment	Time	64.84	2	32.24	71.06	0.001	0.79
	Group and time interaction	42.63	2	21.32	46.98	0.001	0.72
Job compatibility	Time	1473.61	2	436.81	85.40	0.001	0.82
	Group and time interaction	909.30	2	454.65	52.70	0.001	0.75
Organizational citizenship behavior	Time	551.54	2	275.82	43	0.001	0.70
	Group and time interaction	334.80	2	167.40	26.10	0.001	0.59
Strategic thinking	Time	1206.57	2	603.29	106.32	0.001	0.85
	Group and time interaction	755.83	2	377.92	66.60	0.001	0.79
Knowledge management	Time	1330.36	2	665.18	178.35	0.001	0.90
	Group and time interaction	816.03	2	408.02	109.40	0.001	0.85
Job self-efficacy	Time	993.72	2	496.86	10.27	0.001	0.36
	Group and time interaction	648.93	2	324.46	6.71	0.001	0.27

Table 5 and F's results show a significant difference between the mean scores of the three stages of pre-test, post-test and follow-up of job satisfaction, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy. Therefore, organizational intelligence training had a significant effect on job satisfaction, job attachment, job adaptation, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy. This effect had significant stability on these variables after three months.

Table 6. Results of LSD Post Hoc Test Comparison of Mean Scores of Three Stages of Pre-Test, Post-Test and Follow-Up Test of Job Satisfaction, Job Attachment, Job Adjustment, Organizational Citizenship Behavior, Strategic Thinking, Knowledge Management and Job Self-Efficacy

Variable	Groups	Mean difference	Significance level
Job satisfaction	Pre-test – post-test	-5.45	0.001
	Pre-test – follow-up	-6	0.001
Job attachment	Pre-test – post-test	-1.45	0.001
	Pre-test – follow-up	-1.70	0.001
Job compatibility	Pre-test – post-test	-7.90	0.001
	Pre-test – follow-up	-8.95	0.001
Organizational citizenship behavior	Pre-test – post-test	-4.80	0.001
	Pre-test – follow-up	-5.70	0.001
Strategic thinking	Pre-test – post-test	-6.60	0.001
	Pre-test – follow-up	-8.15	0.001
Knowledge management	Pre-test – post-test	-7.30	0.001
	Pre-test – follow-up	-8.75	0.001
Job self-efficacy	Pre-test – post-test	-6.30	0.001
	Pre-test – follow-up	-6.60	0.001

According to the LSD post hoc test results in table 6, the post-test and follow-up scores of job satisfaction, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management, and

job self-efficacy were significantly higher pre-test scores, indicating the effect of training. Organizational intelligence has been based on the mentioned variables and the stability of this training.

Discussion

One of the perhaps unique and new tools for organizations to survive among their competitors is to have comprehensive knowledge of all environmental factors affecting the organization, namely organizational intelligence whose measurement could identify the organization's strengths and weaknesses affecting the organization and thereby help the organization in measuring and determining the degree of progress in achieving its goals. The findings of the study on the effects of organizational intelligence training on the job and organizational variables (job satisfaction, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy) of Iraqi sports managers show a significant difference. Among the mean scores of the three stages of pre-test, post-test and follow-up test, there were job satisfaction, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy. Therefore, it can be said that organizational intelligence training had a significant effect on the variables of job satisfaction, job attachment, job adaptation, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management and job self-efficacy, and this effect had significant stability after three months. According to the post hoc test results, the post-test and follow-up scores of job satisfaction, job attachment, job adjustment, organizational citizenship behavior, strategic thinking, knowledge management, and job self-efficacy were significantly higher than the pre-test scores suggesting the effect of intelligence training and the sustainability of such training.

Although no research has been done on the topic, i.e., organizational intelligence training on organizational and job variables, research has been done on the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. Accordingly, the results of the present study can be in line with the results of Shawardi (2021), Chehrazi (2019), Kavehi (2018), Alizadeh, KalatehSeifri and Abu Jafari (2018), Sadeghi, Mehdi Khani, Nazem and Nazem (2016), BadriAzarin, Khodadadi, AlamiKashki and Sarlab (2016), KhajehKokolaki (2012), Rezaei (2011), Beikzadeh, Alaei and Eskandari (2010), Malekzadeh (2009), Salasel (2009), Barat Dastjerdi and Bazai (2010), Relative (2007), Kashif (2006), SattariGhahfarkhi (2006), Askim (2019), Lefter, Permrino and Asilakkeh (2019), Dari Foss (2019), Libutz (2019), Sargent and Terry (2018), Callaway (2018), Ryan (2017), Lord and Shandrick (2017) and Al-Bakhtar (2015).

The research findings suggest that the corporate intelligence training could guarantee long-term excellence for organizations and improve employee performance. In fact, the training to employees is a driving force for the organization's talent and capacity to move the mental ability and focus that ability to achieve the organizational mission in an intelligent organization that enables people to perform their duties properly and believe in the validity of the business and organizational goals. In the theory of classical economics in the field of competitive advantage, it is stated that there is a need to add the thinking power to the organization, so organizational intelligence training should always be considered a priority. In addition, organizational intelligence training makes the organization act smarter in the current situation so as not to lag behind the competition in the field of science and technology production. Thus, training organizational intelligence to the workforce as a strategic resource could maintain this resource and place them in order to improve job and organizational variables and cause them not to engage with issues intelligently and fully serve the organization with the skills they gained from training organizational intelligence.

From another angle, we can refer to Al-Barakht (2010) theory. Al-Barakht believes that merely hiring and employing smart people with very high brainpower cannot guarantee the organization's success and progress compared to its competitors. After all, when smart people in an organization come together, the organization's mental slowness happens because each of such intelligent people acts individually and thus fails to create a concept for organizational success and excellence. The result would be some unwanted consequences that are not in the organization's interest. What is needed is to cultivate and apply organizational intelligence training at all organization levels and thus improve the job and organizational variables widely in the organization. Therefore, organizational intelligence training to identify and paying attention to this issue as an effective criterion in the organization's success and creating a favorable organizational environment for active participation of employees and committed managers is fully felt. When people know that their ideas, experiences and suggestions are paid attention, they feel more satisfied, attached, and committed to their organization. In this way, they excel and increase their productivity and the organization could use all the knowledge and redouble its efforts.

Sports organizations are the primary custodians of sports in any country, and their performance affects all social, cultural and family dimensions of individuals. Their good performance is a prerequisite for achieving a healthy and developed society. On the contrary, its low performance could lead to various social and cultural deficiencies. The diversity of sports, cultures, tastes and sports facilities in the country have vastly complicated sports organizations' work. The management work in such organizations is also very complex and cannot be managed successfully without intelligence. Undoubtedly, sports organizations must be equipped with high organizational intelligence to move their mental power to achieve organizational goals; in this direction, organizational intelligence training is instrumental. It could be argued confidently that organizational intelligence solutions can increase sports organizations' competitiveness and differentiate them from other organizations. This solution allows sports organizations to take advantage of competitive advantage and leadership by using existing information. In such a way, it enhances the possibility of better understanding the customers' demands and needs as well as managing a better communication with them.

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